

STUDIES ON CADMIUM IODIDE COMPLEXES

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The complex formation of cadmium iodide by the thermometric method has been studied. From the breaks in the curves it is inferred that the complex ions CdI_4'' and CdI_5''' exist in solution.

The peculiar behaviour of cadmium iodide in cryoscopy and conductivity indicates the auto-complex formation in solution (Wienland, "Einführung in die Chemie der complex-verbindungen," Stuttgart, 1924, p. 423). Molecular conductivity at dilution $v=128$ shows it to be a two-ion compound, although at higher dilutions it behaves as a three-ion compound. Hittorf (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1859, 106, 526) from the transport experiment in water solution concluded that cadmium iodide is the cadmium salt of the complex hydro-cadmi-iodic acid $H_2(CdI_4)$. According to McBain (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1905, 11, 215) in concentrated solutions, the ions Cd^{++} and CdI_2' and in dilute solutions, the ions Cd^{++} and I' exist. It has been found from the boiling and freezing point experiments that the observed molecular weight of cadmium iodide is normal i.e., calculated molecular weight 366.27. This can, however, be explained by both the formulae $Cd(CdI_2)_2$ and $Cd(CdI_4)$. In order to distinguish whether either of the complexes is present or both in solution the author has employed thermometric titration (CdI_2 and KI ; $CdSO_4$ and KI) method which is one of the most sensitive physical methods so far known.

EXPERIMENTAL

The thermometric arrangement is the same as that has been described in a previous paper of the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 23, 147). The reagents used were of 'Analar' quality. Standard solutions were prepared by direct weighing and they were further checked by estimating cadmium as $CdNH_4PO_4$, H_2O and iodide with silver nitrate volumetrically.

TABLE I

KI soln.=5M. CdI_2 soln.=0.5M, taken=40 c.c. (Fig. 1).

KI added,	Temp.	Diff. in temp.	Total diff (in temp.)
0 c.c.	2.720°	0.000°	0.000°
1	2.670	0.050	0.050
2	2.610	0.060	0.110
3	2.530	0.060	0.170
4	2.490	0.060	0.230
5	2.425	0.065	0.295
6	2.360	0.065	0.360
7	2.300	0.060	0.420
8	2.250	0.050	0.470
9	2.230	0.020	0.490
10	2.230	0.000	0.490
11	2.230	0.000	0.490
12	2.240	-0.010	0.480
13	2.275	-0.035	0.445
14	2.310	-0.035	0.410
15	2.345	-0.035	0.375
16	2.380	-0.035	0.340
18	2.450	-0.070	0.270

TABLE II

KI soln. = 4.762*M*. CdI₂ soln. = 0.25*M*, taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 2).

KI added.	Temp.	Diff. in temp.	Total diff. (in temp.)
0 c.c.	2.945°	0.000°	0.000°
1	2.920	0.025	0.025
2	2.880	0.040	0.065
3	2.840	0.040	0.105
4	2.800	0.040	0.145
4.5	2.790	0.010	0.155
5.0	2.790	0.000	0.155
5.5	2.790	0.000	0.155
6.0	2.790	0.000	0.155
7.0	2.810	-0.020	0.135
7.5	2.830	-0.020	0.115
8.0	2.850	-0.020	0.095
9.0	2.890	-0.040	0.055
10.0	2.930	-0.040	0.015

TABLE III

KI soln. = 2.5*M*. CdI₂ soln. = 0.25*M*, taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 3).

KI added,	Temp.	Diff. in temp.	Total diff. (in temp.)
0 c.c.	2.080°	0.000°	0.000°
1	2.070	0.010	0.010
2	2.035	0.035	0.045
3	2.000	0.035	0.080
4	1.965	0.035	0.115
5	1.930	0.035	0.150
6	1.895	0.035	0.185
7	1.865	0.030	0.215
8	1.845	0.020	0.235
9	1.825	0.020	0.265
10	1.820	0.005	0.260
11	1.820	0.000	0.260
12	1.820	0.000	0.260
14	1.830	-0.010	0.250
16	1.840	-0.010	0.240
18	1.850	-0.010	0.230
20	1.860	-0.010	0.220

TABLE IV

KI soln. = 2.5*M*. CdI₂ soln. = *M*/6, taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 4).

KI added.	Temp.	Diff. in temp.	Total diff. (in temp.)
0 c.c.	2.825°	0.000°	0.000°
1	2.795	0.030	0.030
2	2.750	0.045	0.075
3	2.705	0.045	0.120
4	2.665	0.040	0.160
5	2.630	0.035	0.195
5.5	2.615	0.015	0.210
6.0	2.600	0.015	0.225
6.5	2.585	0.015	0.240
7.0	2.570	0.015	0.255
7.5	2.560	0.010	0.265
8.0	2.550	0.010	0.275
10.0	2.540	0.010	0.285
12.0	2.530	0.010	0.295

TABLE V

CdI₂ soln.=1.5*M*. KI soln.=0.3*M*, taken=40 c.c. (Fig. 5).

CdI ₂ added.	Temp.	Diff. in temp.	Total diff. (in temp.)
0.0 c.c.	2.930°	0.000°	0.000°
0.5	2.890	0.040	0.040
1.0	2.845	0.045	0.085
1.5	2.800	0.045	0.130
2.0	2.760	0.040	0.170
2.5	2.730	0.030	0.200
3.0	2.700	0.030	0.230
3.5	2.680	0.020	0.250
4.0	2.665	0.015	0.265
4.5	2.655	0.010	0.275
5.0	2.645	0.010	0.285
6.0	2.630	0.015	0.300
7.0	2.615	0.015	0.315
8.0	2.600	0.015	0.330
9.0	2.585	0.015	0.345
10.0	2.570	0.015	0.360

TABLE VI

KI soln.=3.0303*M*. CdSO₄ soln.=*M*/3, taken=40c.c. (Fig. 6).

KI added.	Temp.	Diff. in temp.	Total diff. (in temp.)
0 c.c.	4.510°	0.000°	0.000°
1	4.445	0.065	0.065
2	4.360	0.085	0.150
3	4.290	0.070	0.220
4	4.230	0.060	0.280
5	4.175	0.055	0.335
6	4.120	0.055	0.390
7	4.065	0.055	0.445
8	4.010	0.055	0.500
9	3.960	0.050	0.550
10	3.910	0.050	0.600
11	3.860	0.050	0.650
12	3.820	0.040	0.690
13	3.780	0.040	0.730
14	3.740	0.040	0.770
15	3.700	0.040	0.810
16	3.670	0.030	0.840
17	3.645	0.025	0.865
18	3.625	0.020	0.885
19	3.620	0.005	0.890
20	3.620	0.000	0.890
21	3.620	0.000	0.890
22	3.620	0.000	0.890
23	3.635	-0.015	0.875
24	3.645	-0.010	0.865
26	3.670	-0.025	0.840
28	3.700	-0.030	0.810
30	3.730	-0.030	0.780

Each titration has been repeated twice and the results agree with each other very closely.

DISCUSSION

Although the shape of the curves changes with concentration of cadmium iodide solution it is peculiarly interesting to note that the breaks in all the curves are at the points corresponding Cd-iodide : K-iodide=1 : 2 and Cd-iodide : K-iodide 1 : 3. Thus the first breaks in the curves in Figs. 1 to 4 and second break in the curve in Fig. 5 indicate definitely the existence of the complex ion CdI₄²⁻ in solution and the reaction at the break point is

With further increase of KI_2 concentration, the complex ion CdI_4'' becomes CdI_5'' as follows

and so the second breaks in the curves in Figs. 1-4, and first break in Fig. 5 are observed.

FIG. 1.
KI soln. = 5M
 CdI_2 soln. = M/2, 40 c.c.

FIG. 2.
KI soln. = 4.762M
 CdI_2 soln. = M/4, 40 c.c.

The absence of any break in the curves corresponding to $CdI_2 : KI = 1 : 1$ indicates that

FIG. 3.
KI soln. = 2.5M.
 CdI_2 soln. = M/4, 40 c.c.

possibly the ion CdI_5' does not exist in solution and if it exists at all it is almost completely dissociated into Cd^{++} and I^- . The results of the author are in agreement with those obtained from other physical methods, namely cryoscopy by Urbain and Cornec (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1919, 25, 137), absorption spectra by Job (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 1108), ebullioscopy by Burion and Mile O. Hun (*Compt. rend.*, 1930, 191, 97), phase rule by Herring (*Compt. rend.*, 1933, 197, 143) and Raman spectra by Dalwaulle, Francois and Wiemann (*Compt. rend.*, 1938, 206, 187; 1938, 208, 184). Cornec and Urbain have shown not only the existence of the complex ion CdI_4'' but also have

observed with the system CdI_2-HI , that the ion CdI_3' is very unstable in moist air and so it is evident that the existence of the complex ion CdI_3' is not expected in solution as is indicated by the present experiment. Therefore the conclusion of McBain that Cd-miumiodide exists in concentrated solutions as Cd^{++} and CdI_3' is not quite correct and is against the results obtained by different physical methods. It is further to be noted that no mention of the complex ion CdI_3'' in solution is found in the literature, although from phase rule study Herring has isolated the compound $CdI_2 \cdot 3KI \cdot 4H_2O$ in the solid phase. In order to see whether any other Cd salt, when titrated with KI, gives indications about the existence of the complex ions

CdI_3'' and CdI_3''' , Cd-sulphate solution has been titrated with KI solution. Fig. 6 (for

FIG. 5.

KI soln. = 0.3M. CdI_2 soln. = 1.5M, 40 c.c.

curve, although it is expected to be present if the complex ion CdI_4'' is formed in solution according to the equation,

FIG. 4.

KI soln. = 2.5M. CdI_2 soln. = M/6, 40 c.c.

$CdSO_4-KI$) shows four breaks corresponding to $CdSO_4 : KI = 1 : 1, 1 : 3, 1 : 4$ and $1 : 5$. The break corresponding to $1 : 1$ is due to the formation of the complex $K_2Cd(SO_4)_2$ in solution according to the equations given below :

Adding

The third and fourth breaks corresponding to $1 : 4$ and $1 : 5$ are due to the ions CdI_4'' and CdI_5''' . But the second break corresponding to $1 : 3$ is not due to the ion CdI_3'' , as no break corresponding to this ion formation has been observed in CdI_2-KI -system. Further it is to be noted that the break corresponding to $CdSO_4 : KI = 1 : 2$ has not been observed in the

FIG. 6.

KI soln. = 3.0303*M*. CdSO₄ soln. = *M*/3, 40 c.c.

This is explained by the fact that a certain amount of the complex ion CdI_3^{2-} has been formed at the point $\text{CdSO}_4 : \text{KI} = 1 : 1$, and so when further KI solution is added, a portion of it reacts with $\text{Cd}(\text{CdI}_4)$ and converts it into $\text{K}_2(\text{CdI}_4)$ and the remaining portion reacts with $\text{K}_2\text{Cd}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ converting it to $\text{Cd}(\text{CdI}_4)$. Thus if only $\text{K}_2(\text{CdI}_4)$ would have been formed, the break would have appeared at the point corresponding to $\text{CdSO}_4 : \text{KI} = 1 : 4$ and again if only $\text{Cd}(\text{CdI}_4)$ would have been formed, the break at the point corresponding to $\text{CdSO}_4 : \text{KI} = 1 : 2$ would have been noted. Since both the processes are taking place simultaneously *i.e.*, breaks corresponding to 1 : 4 and 1 : 2, the break near about 2 : 6 or 1 : 3 appears. The definite indication of the existence of the complex ion CdI_3^{2-} in solution by the thermometric method shows that by this method not only the complex ion predicted by other methods are noted but in addition where other physical methods fail, it can be used with great success provided the heat change is sufficient.

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